

Destination Attributes – Its Role on Constructing Image of Bandung as A MICE Destination in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The MICE business continuously grow. Therefore, the MICE organizer provides an assessment of the city's destination attributes. The purpose of this study is to disclose the forming factors of the destination. This study uses multiple regression analysis methods with a sample of 150 respondents. Two destination attributes as affordability and activities do not significantly influence the image formation of Bandung as a MICE destination. The simultaneous effect is 88.4%, while the other un-observed factors influence 11.6%. Thus, the availability of complete and high-quality destination attributes in Bandung will improve the city's image as a MICE destination. Furthermore, it enables Bandung to compete with the other MICE destinations in Indonesia.

Keywords: image, attribute, destination.

INTRODUCTION

According to the World Tourism Organization (WTO), tourism is one of the fastest growing industries in the world. Tourism is even a significant source of state revenue. The United Nation-World Tourism Organization (UN-WTO) provides a favorable view of tourism as a key to development, prosperity, and welfare. The burgeoning number of the opened and invested new tourist destinations transforms tourism as a critical driver for social-economic advancement through export revenues, job & enterprise creation, and infrastructure development. Currently, the tourism business develops well. Also, it tends to increase from year to year.

For more than six decades, tourism has developed and diversified into one of the fastest growing economic sectors in the world. Tourism

is a relatively stable sector with regular growth rates over time, despite the occasional shocks. This condition shows the sector's strength and resilience. The United Nation-World Tourism Organization (UN-WTO) 2017 shows the report. Foreign tourist arrivals increased from 25 million in 1950 to 278 million in 1980, 674 million in 2000, and 1,235 million in 2016. Likewise, revenues from international tourism by destinations around the world have increased from the US \$ 2 billion in 1950 to the US \$ 104 billion in 1980, the US \$ 495 billion in 2000, and the US \$ 1,220 billion in 2016.

The data shows the development of the number of tourists who travel internationally with various destinations or types of tourism activities. One of them is a trip for business purposes.

The business tour was initially aimed at trading, selling and carrying goods to consumers. Currently, it develops into a business tour which aims to attend conferences, business events interspersed with fun activities.

Both domestic and international tourists activities have different destinations. According to UN-WTO, the activities are categorized into leisure & recreation, other purpose tourism, including visiting friends and relatives (VFR), religion, study & health tourism, and business and professional, including Meeting, Incentive, Conference and Exhibition (MICE) activities. In other words, the travel destination consists of trips for fun and recreation, visiting relatives (the phenomenon of going home during holidays), religious purposes, learning and health and sightseeing trips for business and professional purposes, such as trips to attend meetings, incentive trips, attending conferences and exhibitions. In this case, the MICE tour includes travel with business and professional purposes.

Based on data from Euromonitor (2013), the arrival rate of MICE tourists in Indonesia in 2012 approximately 184,600 people out of a total of 3.6 million business travel. This number has an excellent development compared to MICE tourist arrivals in 2007 of 88,800 tourists from 2.1 million.

The Indonesian Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy also noted although the number of MICE tourists is rather small, the data from the International Conference and Congress Association, MICE tourists' expenditure is seven times larger than leisure travelers. If leisure travelers expenditure is the US \$ 1,634 or around Rp. 18,200,000, - in a visit, MICE tourists spend around Rp. 127,400,000. In the annual International Congress and Convention Association and International Association Meetings (ICCA) in 2017, a professional association in the field of congress and convention noted that for Indonesia, in 2015 it was ranked forty-three (43) with a total of seventy-eight (78) international meetings and in

2016 experienced an increase to forty (40) ranks with a total of ninety-four (94) international meetings.

In order to build the MICE business in Indonesia, the Government of Indonesia Based on Tourism Regulation No. 29 of 2015 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Tourism in 2015 - 2019 and Regulation of Tourism No. 5 of 2017 concerning the Guidelines for the Implementation of MICE, the Directorate-General for Tourism Destination Development at the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy has established sixteen (16) cities and regions as MICE Cities. They are Bali, Makassar, Batam, Yogyakarta, Jakarta, Medan, Semarang, Solo, Surabaya, Balikpapan, Palembang, Padang, Manado, Lombok, Bintan, and Bandung.

The Directorate-General of Tourism Destination Development at the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy also has mapped sixteen MICE destinations in Indonesia using nine (9) criteria: accessibility, stakeholder support, exciting places, accommodation facilities, meeting facilities, exhibition facilities, image destinations, environmental conditions, and HR professionals.

The government also has ranked some cities as MICE destinations. The mapping and measurement results are obtained by using the measurement scale. The evaluation approach based on self-evaluation by stakeholders and assessment by the experts are the base of the measurement scale.

According to the rank based on the scale of the nine (9) criteria of MICE destinations, Bandung is ranked as the sixth (6) of sixteen (16) MICE destinations in Indonesia. In 2010, the International Congress and Convention Association and the International Association Meetings (ICCA) conducted the other assessments and ranked Bandung in the 309th position with a total of five meetings (5) meetings. On the contrary, in 2011 and 2012, Bandung was not included in the MICE

Destination City ranking. In 2013, Bandung re-entered the ICCA ranking and fell to the 328th position with six (6) meetings. Whereas in 2014 and 2015, Bandung was not entered in the MICE Destination City ranking. In 2016 Bandung re-entered the ICCA ranking and got the 301st position with eight (8) meetings.

Bandung as a MICE City has an international record due to the success of organizing the Asia Africa Conference in April 1955. In this case, Bandung became one of the historic cities in organizing conference activities. Bandung is a potential MICE city in Indonesia although it experiences a downturn in the International Congress and Convention Association rank.

Bandung Government realizes their MICE tourism potential and seeks to find the best way to develop the tourism. Regarding MICE tourism, Ridwan Kamil the Mayor of Bandung states tourism promotion in Bandung does bring not only the regular tourists but also the quality tourists. Besides, he also promotes the concept of MICE (Meeting, Incentives, Conferencing, Exhibition), urban tourism and resorts tourism.

Tourism entrepreneurs feel optimistic about the development of the MICE business in Bandung. Handrio Utomo, the former General Manager of the Grand Royal Panghegar Hotel Bandung, stated that Bandung could be one of the MICE destinations for corporations in the next few years. If Bandung tourism industry creatively manages the MICE market, it is not impossible Bandung becomes the center of MICE in the country. Tourism entrepreneurs in Bandung must be able to collaborate MICE activities with some derivatives of other tourism activities. The goal is to boost the rate of tourists to the city.

Based on data, it can be concluded that Bandung has the opportunity to develop the MICE business. Besides, there are some shortcomings concerning facilities that cause declining of MICE tourism in Bandung. Regional governments continue to strive to improve

deficiencies in tourism development in West Java and develop tourism potential in the city of Bandung, including in efforts to develop MICE tourism in the city of Bandung. In other words, the Bandung City government continues to strive to increase the number of MICE tourist visits that will have an impact on economic progress in Bandung.

Bandung becomes a potential MICE city in Indonesia even though it experienced a downturn in the ranking of International Congress and Convention Association. If the government of Bandung wants to promote MICE tourism successfully, then Bandung must be different from the competitors, or positively do the positioning to the tourists.

In organizing a MICE activity, the desire of participants to attend a MICE activity, choose a MICE destination, the intensity of visiting is closely related to the image of the destination. Some experts believe the selection of a destination by a tourist, including MICE tourists is often influenced by the push and pull factors (Gallarza, Saura & García, 2002; Pike, 2002; Chen & Tsai, 2007; Prayag & Ryan, 2011; Yousefi & Marzuki, 2015)

Push factors refer to the motivation of tourists, for example, the need to get out of their daily activities, the desire to interact with others while pull factor relates to factors that influence a person, when, where and how people travel, including to attend a business tour activity especially MICE tourism which is closely related to the appearance of appearance factors, tourist attractions and attributes of the destination itself (Nikjoo & Ketabi, 2015).

Lee and Back (2007) argue the organizers select the destination attributes such as accessibility, tourist/entertainment attractions, affordability, availability of facilities, security & safety, and quality of service. According to Chiu & Ananzeh (2012) who cite the opinions of Kang, Suh & Jo (2005); Lee & Back, (2007) that the attributes of MICE destinations consist of

affordable price, tourist attraction, accessibility, amenities, activities, and accountability.

The destination attributes have a role of as a pulling factor for an organizer to arrange an activity in a place or city. Besides, the destination attributes shape the image of a destination in which a MICE activity takes place. Some experts conduct studies about the importance of destination attributes in shaping the image of a destination. Oppermann (1996) conducted and proven the importance of a MICE destination attribute. Lee and Back (2007) tested the role of MICE destination attributes in shaping the overall image of a destination. The image can be defined as a perception phenomenon that is formed through the reasons of the consumer and the consumer's emotional interpretation which has a cognitive component (knowledge & belief) and effective (feeling) (Konecnik, 2004).

Several studies tried to measure the image of a destination. It is hard to do since it involves some visible components such as physical aspects, geography, panorama, facilities for tourists, climate. Also, the study also involves tourists' emotional aspects or interviewee to assess the destination image.

In this study, the components of a destination image in the cognitive imagery aspect adapted from Chiu & Ananzeh (2012). They consist of knowledge from tourists/organizers regarding the atmosphere, political and social factors, facilities for tourists, natural resources, public infrastructure, economic factors and culture (Beerli & Martin, 2004; Tasci, 2007; Campo-Martínez, Garau-Vadell & Martínez-Ruiz, 2010; Allameh et al., 2015) while the affective imagery aspect consists of a feeling of excitement-not enthusiasm, pleasant feeling-unpleasant, exiting-boring feeling and feeling relaxed-distressed (Beerli & Martin, 2004; Kaplanidou, 2006; Qu, Kim & Im, 2011; Agapito, Oom do Valle & da Costa Mendes, 2013).

Bandung as a MICE destination already has developable destination attributes to form a positive destination image. Various uniqueness, cultural richness, numerous natural attractions and culinary tourism in Bandung make it a famous tourism city. Moreover, Bandung represents Indonesia in the international world. Bandung has been registered in the World Tourism City Federation (WTCTF) with 106 other cities in the world. Bandung has also been confirmed as a world tourism destination at the WTCTF meeting in Beijing, September 12, 2017.

Attributes from a destination are also crucial for the organizer who will hold a MICE event in a place or city. Destination attributes are essential when the organizer offers MICE activities to tourists or customers. For example, when a meeting planner will hold a meeting and select a city, the first step is considering the attributes of a destination. Some literature and research state the organizer assesses the attributes of a destination before organizing a MICE activity.

FRAMEWORK

MICE acronyms have become widely known by the community. Rogers (2003) describes MICE as the terminology used for meetings, incentives, conferences, and exhibitions. In this case, meetings mean discussion, incentives refer to incentive trips, conferences refer to the activities of reference and exhibition means exhibition activities. The concept of the MICE business refers to Law No. 10 in 2009 about Tourism which states the business of organizing meetings, incentive trips, conferences and exhibitions is a business that provides services for a meeting of a group of people, organizes trips for employees and business partners in return for their achievements, and organizes exhibitions in order to disseminate information and promotion of goods and services on a national, regional and international scale.

Destinations are tourist destinations in which the process of consuming tourism products and

services takes place. Wilde & Cox (2008) cites the opinions of several experts regarding the destination itself. According to Page & Connell (2006) in general, the concept of a destination can be built to represent geographically, for example, a group of countries, a country, a region of a country, a city, a rural area, a resort area. The destination image is an essential aspect to develop a city as a tourist destination, including MICE tourism. Destination images can be described as a whole perspective of potential tourists and visitors to the existence of a place or city. According to Dimanche (2003), destination image is highly dependent on internal and external environmental factors of the opinion giver or assessment.

Corte & Micera (2007) emphasize the importance of actual images that demanded by the tourists from a destination and in the minds of potential tourists who will visit a destination. Images attached to a tourist occur through several processes that are strongly influenced by defined factors. The process of image formation can differ from one person to another.

Each tourist form the individual perceptions of a destination based on cognitive aspects and affective aspects. The component of destination image in the aspect of cognitive imagery adapted from Chiu & Ananzeh (2012) consists of knowledge from tourists and organizer regarding the atmosphere, political and social factors, facilities for tourists, natural resources, public infrastructure, economic and cultural factors (Beerli & Martin, 2004; San Martín & Del Bosque, 2008) While the affective imagery aspect consists of enthusiastic-disinterested, pleasant-unpleasant feeling, exciting-boring and relax-distressed (Beerli & Martin, 2004; Yüksel & Akgül, 2007).

Stepchenkova & Morrison (2006) affirm the relationship between cognitive aspects and affective aspects. There is general agreement that the destination image is a variety of forms and appearances. Moreover, it creates a composition consists of evaluating cognitive and

affective aspects that are closely interrelated into a general impression.

RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, the author uses quantitative descriptive research methods and applies multiple regression analysis techniques. The author attempts to find out the role of destination attributes in forming the cognitive and affective components from the Bandung's destination image as a MICE destination and describe it for further analysis. This study uses the theoretical approach and opinions from several experts, regarding variables X and Y variables and adapts from previous studies made by Chiu and Ananzeh (2012). To collect the data of this research, the author searched the data through the questionnaires, literature studies and interviews.

The population and sample selection in the study are ASPERAPI members since the members are meeting organizers, incentive travel organizers, exhibition organizers, and conference organizers. The other members consist of stakeholders and service providers who are involved in organizing meetings, incentive trips, exhibition and conference organizers. The sampling technique used by the author is a non-probability sampling technique by using conventional techniques. The samples in this study were 150 respondents. The author uses descriptive statistical and multiple regression analysis techniques.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The business unit represented by the respondent is basically used to provide an explanation of the business activities carried out by Asperapi Members. The business unit identifies the business scope as well as the character of the owned business and also as a comparison of each business unit. The following data is a description of the business unit

represented by the respondent. The majority of business units consists of the organizer with 79%. The small number of business units 'were represented by stand contractors and entertainment, each of them is 3%.

The description of the respondent's data can be used to find out how the respondent acknowledges each indicator variable. The respondents' response scores to twenty-one (21) items regarding the attributes of MICE destinations reveals that the attributes are in the excellent category. The respondents' response scores to thirteen (13) statements regarding the Bandung's image shows that the Bandung's image is in a proper category.

The calculation gets the constant values and regression coefficients as show at figure 1. This is the multiple linear regression equation:

$$Y = 3,495 + 0,006 X1 + 0,616 X2 + 0,568 X3 + 1,762 X4 + 0,167 X5 + 0,526 X6$$

The coefficient of determination can be seen from the R square value of 0.884. This value means the influence of variables X1, X2, X3, X4, X5, and X6 on Bandung's image (Y) is 88.4%. The rest of 11.6% is influenced by the other factors that are not observed.

In MICE Destination Attribute with 21 statements and 150 respondents, the total score is 11599. The length of the interval for each category is 2520 and within interval 10710 and 13230. The total of respondents' scores shows that the attributes of MICE destinations are in a good category. Respondents' positive feedback regarding Bandung destination attributes can be a positive aspect for the development of the MICE business in Bandung.

Based on the theory which is explained in an operational variable, there are six (6) Bandung's destination attribute variables. Bandung's image variable total score is 7131 in the range of 6630-8190 and categorized as good. This finding means Bandung as a MICE destination has a good image. The image of a destination is generated based on knowledge or cognitive

dimensions and feelings or affective dimensions of tourists. In this context, the respondents are members of ASPERAPI. Knowledge or cognitive dimensions consist of the knowledge of respondents in terms of atmosphere, political and social factors, facilities for tourists, natural resources, public infrastructure, economic and cultural factors whereas the affective dimension consists of a feeling of enthusiastic-disinterested, pleasant-unpleasant feeling, exciting-boring, and relax-distressed.

The calculation of the coefficient of determination with R-square value is 0.884. It shows Bandung's attributes destination which consists of affordability, attractions, accessibility, amenities, activities, and accountability affect the image formation of Bandung by 88.4%, while the rest 11.6% is influenced by the other factors that are not observed.

The other factors that influence the formation of the image as adopted by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy through the Directorate General of Tourism Destination Development of the Republic of Indonesia in previous research are about risk indicators and destination marketing.

The magnitude of the influence of destination attributes on the formation of the Bandung's destination image as a MICE destination in Indonesia defines that Bandung will be more successful in managing the MICE business if the management of destination attributes is excellent. This condition has an impact on the creation of Bandung as one of Indonesia's favorite MICE destinations. In other words, the increasing image of Bandung which is influenced by the fulfillment of destination attributes will also raise the rating of MICE destinations from the 6th rank of 16 MICE destinations in Indonesia.

Based on data from MICE Center (2013), Bandung's ranking under the independent assessment and experts' assessment in the MICE field is ranked 6th below Bali, Jakarta, Surabaya, Yogyakarta, and Makassar. This fact is also reinforced by Govers, Go & Kumar (2007)

that with the effects of globalization, MICE business competition has shifted from competition between companies to competition between destinations.

Figure 1
Result of regression

CONCLUSION

This study found that respondents' responses were good regarding the destination attributes of Bandung. According to the descriptive analysis, it was found that the respondents' responses on Bandung's image were good and based on the T-Test results, the accessibility attributes of destination and destination attribute activities partially did not significantly influence the image of Bandung as a MICE destination in Indonesia. While the attributes of tourist attraction destinations,

accessibility, amenities, and accountability partially have a significant effect on the image formation of the city of Bandung.

The advice for Bandung's Government is the affordability attribute in terms of price to attend a MICE activity. The Bandung's Government can help by providing tax incentives and subsidies to the organizers who will hold MICE activities in Bandung and cooperate with the private sector to provide the convention building. Tourist attraction attributes related to the management and arrangement of tourist attractions with regard to originality aspects, the authenticity of

tourist attractions. Accessibility attributes that concern for the easiness of reaching Bandung, including the location of MICE activities. Improving the efforts to reduce the traffic jam in Bandung is essential. Organizing the facilities aspects is also important. The construction of MICE facilities adopts the concept of the facility package. To sum up, building MICE facilities should be made within an area.

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